

RESEARCH

Open Access

Data analytics to prevent retail credit card fraud: empirical evidence from Latin America

Leidy Tatiana Rugeles Diaz¹

*Correspondence:
sergio.nanez@ucavila.es

¹ Department of DataScience,
Vana, Bogotá, Colombia

² Faculty of Social and Legal
Sciences, Department
of Economics, Dekis Research
Group, Catholic University
of Ávila, Ávila, Spain

³ Facultad de Economía
y Empresa. Universidad
Internacional de La Rioja,
Avenida de la Paz, 137,
Logroño 26006, Spain

Abstract

Reducing the risk of fraud in credit card transactions is crucial for the competitiveness of companies, especially in Latin American countries. This study aims to establish measures for preventing and detecting fraud in the use of credit cards in shops through analytical methods (data mining, machine learning and artificial intelligence). To achieve this objective, the study employs a predictive methodology using descriptive and exploratory statistics and frequency, frequency & monetary (RFM) classification techniques, differentiating between SMEs and large businesses via cluster analysis and supervised models. A dataset of 221,292 card records from a Latin American merchant payment gateway for the year 2022 is used. For fraud alerts, the classification model has been selected for small and medium-sized merchants, and the multilayer perceptron (MLP) neural network has been selected for large merchants. Random forest or Gini decision tree models have been selected as backup models for retraining. For the detection of punctual fraud patterns, the K-means and partitioning around medoids (PAM) models have been selected, depending on the type of trade. The results revealed that the application of the identified models would have prevented between 48 and 85% of fraud transactions, depending on the trade size. Despite the promising results, continuous updating is recommended, as fraudsters frequently implement new fraud techniques.

Keywords: Fraud prevention, Risk, Competitiveness, Machine learning, Credit cards

JEL Classification: G17, G14, M15, M21

Introduction, theoretical background and research objective

Rapid technological development in recent years and the expansion of e-commerce have markedly increased credit card fraud. In this study, an analysis was carried out using supervised and unsupervised models to classify and predict fraudulent credit card transactions among merchants in Latin America (Ballezza 2007; Balagolla et al. 2021; Ahmed 2022; Lokanan 2022). This research focuses on the timing of the payment gateway (Kim and Kim 2020; Kilay et al. 2022). Preventive measures are provided to reject fraudulent transactions (Barker et al. 2008; Delamaire et al. 2009; Chaudhary et al. 2012), and alerts are generated to warn merchants of recent transactions that have already been approved and are very likely to be fraudulent. In fraud prevention, many manual processes can

be automated and optimized, and even some decisions can be made on the basis of results from models. The concepts of statistics, data mining (Chan et al. 1999; Bhattacharyya et al. 2011; Ernowati et al. 2021), *machine learning* (Sarker 2021; Tiwari et al. 2021; Tanouz et al. 2021; Krishna Rao et al., 2021; Hasan, 2022) and artificial intelligence (Beena et al. 2021; Zhang and Lu 2021; Akinbowale et al. 2022; Alhabib et al. 2024; Vergara et al. 2024, 2025) play crucial roles in optimally preventing fraud. On the other hand, the high rates of credit card fraud in Latin America (Álvarez and Ladino 2021) justify the interest of this region as a territorial unit of study in this research.

Fraudulent operations have affected companies in different countries and many users. Examples include Home Depot in 2014, with 56 million affected users, and Sony in 2011, with 12 million affected users (Al Smadi and Min 2020). Technology means using more sophisticated fraud techniques, but at the same time, it facilitates the development of more effective strategies to combat it. In card transactions, fraud can be defined and can occur in different ways. First, there is theft of the card owner's information and the use of that data to make online purchases (Chen and Lai 2021; Gianotti and Damião da Silva 2021; King et al. 2021; Mekterovic et al. 2021; Siblino et al. 2021). This information theft can be accomplished through phone calls or the financial institution's website (Alatawi 2025). Second, tools that calculate credit card numbers and their expiration dates and card verification value codes (CVVs) are used (Al Smadi and Min 2020; Ernowati et al. 2021; Hasan 2022). Third, bots that perform many transactions simultaneously are used. Fourth, the websites of official shops, banks or merchants should be impersonated (Mekterovic et al. 2021; Siblino et al. 2021). For these reasons, fraud is regulated by legislation in different countries (Sanz-Bas et al. 2021; Nández Alonso et al. 2024). Transactions go through a payment gateway, where all online transactions are handled. Here, the gateway can approve or reject transactions through an anti-fraud module that is managed by people and tools. The approved transactions go through the card issuing bank, which may also have an additional anti-fraud module. These processes help prevent and detect the risk of fraud and are vital factors in gaining a competitive advantage over companies that do not adopt them (Ballezza 2007; Tanouz et al. 2021). In addition, they improve customer experience by offering higher levels of security in payment processing, which can help retain them as customers (Brito et al. 2024). On an economic and developmental level, some authors, such as Bajwa (2017), note that the existence of secure e-commerce is a fundamental element for entrepreneurship and economic development, especially in emerging countries. Additionally, (Tran 2021) indicated that the security of virtual payment transactions is a competitive advantage over merchants, who cannot secure and detect fraud, even for more sustainable trade.

The significant economic implications of credit card fraud have sparked interest in academia. Recently, numerous studies have developed two predominant research approaches: the detection and prediction of credit card fraud and the design of advanced solutions based on new technologies to prevent it. Regarding the first approach, the most recent studies have focused their efforts on the application of machine learning methods for the detection of these fraudulent transactions (Alharbi et al. 2022). Several studies have recently used neural networks to address this issue. Forough and Momtazi (2021) propose a fraud detection model for credit card transactions that combines deep neural networks and probabilistic graphical models. The results obtained in their

study demonstrate significant improvements in fraud detection accuracy and efficiency. Lei et al. (2023) propose a distributed neural network (DDNN) model to detect credit card fraud transactions. They conclude that their proposal improves detection accuracy compared with other models, avoids leakage of private data and reduces handling costs. Huang et al. (2024) proposed a hybrid neural network to detect fraud in credit card transactions on the basis of identity and transaction features. The experimental results show that the method is more efficient. Cherif et al. (2024) developed a method to detect fraud associated with credit card transactions via graphical neurons (GNNs), optimizing feature selection and relationship modeling. The results of the validation of the proposed model support its improved accuracy.

With respect to the second approach, several studies have examined the contribution and application of emerging digital technologies to prevent fraud in credit card transactions. Dadhich et al. (2022) identify fraudulent card payment methods used by cyber-criminals and provide an analysis of systems that can detect and block their action. Chatterjee and Rawat (2024) analyze the role of blockchain technology and federated learning in fraud detection. They conclude that the features of this technology make transactions more transparent, reliable and secure. This helps prevent fraud in the financial industry. Other authors, such as Ogbanufe and Kim (2018), argue that the use of biometric authentication is a more secure solution for credit card authentication, which reduces the number of fraudulent transactions.

Nevertheless, despite these technological advances, Cherif et al. (2023) conclude that there is a lack of sufficient research to address the challenges posed by credit card fraud. Furthermore, nonparametric statistical tests conducted on the dataset—specifically the Kruskal–Wallis test ($H = 256.4$; $p < 0.001$) and the prevalence ratio of fraud ($\chi^2 = 219.3$; $p < 0.001$)—confirm that fraud patterns differ statistically significantly between small, medium, and large businesses, which supports the need to model each stratum separately. These findings justify modeling each business segment separately. This stratified approach also aligns with the literature, which shows that algorithmic performance varies depending on company size and data characteristics. In this context, SMEs have emerged as a particularly critical segment. They are vital to the global economy and all societies. However, they face a complex and challenging environment, as they lag behind in digital transformation in most sectors (Kotios et al. 2022). The detection of anomalous behavior in business process data is crucial for preventing failures that may jeopardize the performance of any organization (Elaziz et al. 2023). Supervised learning techniques are impracticable because of the difficulty of gathering large amounts of labeled business process anomaly data (Elaziz et al. 2023). Recent studies have shown that segmenting companies by size can significantly improve fraud detection accuracy, as fraud patterns, capital constraints, and incentives to report differ across strata. These insights not only justify segmentation for analytical rigor but also inform practical deployment strategies—helping payment processors and fraud analysts allocate resources more effectively across business tiers. For example, approximately 99% of companies worldwide are SMEs and often lack external audits, making them particularly vulnerable to fraud (Ngai et al. 2011). In Latin America, there have even been documented cases of financial statement manipulation to obtain credit lines above actual capacity (Carcillo et al. 2021). In response to such challenges, assembled trees have become the first line of defense:

the random forest outperforms deep networks on Latin American transaction datasets (Carcillo et al. 2021) and SME financial statement audits, where it achieves 97% recovery compared with 92% for an MLP (Kaur et al. 2021). This same conclusion is reached by Bin Sulaiman et al. (2022), who warned that the dense structure of MLPs can lead to inefficiency. Tree ensembles also dominate advertising click fraud (Ziakos and Vlachopoulou 2023); a recent study achieved 95% accuracy with a random forest (Abbas et al. 2025). Cost-sensitive stacking methods—e.g., logistic regression + XGBoost—reduce false positives and expected losses in multinational bank panels (Charizanos et al. 2024; Tumminello et al. 2022). Neural approaches remain attractive for complex nonlinear patterns: an MLP trained on ledgers achieved 93% AUC (Bin Sulaiman et al. 2022)—or 94% according to J. Zhang et al. (2024)—with latency < 20 ms, which is crucial for online microcommerce. However, systematic reviews confirm that shallow tree ensembles or Bayesian models often outperform stand-alone MLPs when the sample size varies greatly across strata (Hastie et al. 2009; Costa and Pedreira 2022; Blockeel et al. 2023). Probabilistic models retain their niche: Naive Bayes does not usually top the rankings, but its deployment without adjustment and transparent likelihood ratios make it popular in low-resource microretail contexts (Viaene et al. 2005; Assaf et al. 2011; Vosseler 2022; Saha et al. 2023). By relaxing independence, Bayesian networks made it possible to reduce false positives in insurance claims (Mary and Claret 2023). Support vector machines (SVMs), although slightly behind ensembles, remain competitive when the attribute space explodes after one-hot encoding of heterogeneous variables, especially when stratified by turnover (Rtayli and Enneya 2020). These findings underscore the importance of aligning the model architecture with both the nature of the data and the operational constraints of the business segment.

Finally, classic clustering still underpins exploratory segmentation. The canonical triad—k-means (MacQueen 1967), PAM with Gower distance (Kaufman and Rousseeuw 1990) and agglomerative linkage (Murtagh and Contreras 2011)—covers spherical, medoid-centered and hierarchical structures, respectively, and is frequently combined with supervised back ends. Together, these studies confirm that no single model dominates universally; rather, aligning algorithmic bias with merchant-size segments (and their fraud cost structure) yields the best trade-off between detection power, interpretability and operational cost (Cybenko 1989).

This research has two fundamental objectives to improve the detection and prevention of fraud in credit card transactions, adapting to the specific needs of small, medium and large merchants.

First, the characteristics of fraudulent transactions are identified to prevent fraud among small, medium and large merchants.

Second, we predict whether recently approved and executed transactions may be fraudulent and determine the likelihood of this occurrence alerting merchants.

This study investigates how machine learning models can improve fraud detection in credit card transactions with merchants in Latin America. The research question is as follows: What is the best method for detecting fraud among small, medium and large merchants in a region?

This research closes a significant gap in the scientific literature by analyzing, for the first time, the best methods according to business size: small, medium or large. The main

contribution of this research is the implementation and evaluation of the multilayer perceptron (MLP) neural network in the context of credit card fraud detection. In contrast to other studies that have focused primarily on more developed regions, our research focuses on Latin America. This region presents specific challenges due to its particular socioeconomic and technological characteristics.

The findings of this study demonstrate that the MLP offers higher predictive accuracy in fraud detection. Owing to its ability to capture nonlinear and complex patterns in transaction data, the MLP is particularly effective for contexts with a high volume of transactions, as is the case in Latin America. While recurrent models are suitable for handling sequential data, the MLP stands out for its ability to detect anomalies in large transactional datasets. In addition to confirming the superior accuracy of the MLP, this study makes a significant contribution by analyzing transactions in SMEs in Latin America, a topic that has not been extensively explored in the literature. Equally important are the practical implications of the findings from a regulatory and policy perspective. The study discusses how financial supervisors can leverage these findings to develop more effective fraud prevention and control policies. This suggests the need for regulations that encourage businesses and financial institutions to adopt advanced fraud detection technologies, such as the MLP, thereby reducing financial losses and enhancing the security of credit card transactions.

Materials and methodology

Materials

The database used in this study includes 221,292 anonymized records of credit card transactions in Latin American merchant payment gateways from 2022. The database consists of 163 columns, of which 1 is the id of the transactions, 24 are categorical, 6 are date, and 132 are numeric, all of which are variables used. The datasets analyzed during the present study are not publicly available due to their ability to collect banking data but are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request. The data were processed in the following way. First, the transactions were anonymized to protect the identity of individuals. The columns were subsequently identified and categorized (as shown in Table 1), and the transactions were filtered. Only transactions approved by the payment gateway and the bank were considered. To balance the data between fraudulent transactions and nonfraudulent transactions, stratified sampling was used.

Methodology

Merchant-size classification (RFM)

To segment merchants, we adapt the classic Recency-Frequency-Monetary (RFM) framework to a fraud prevention context. Numerous studies have shown the effectiveness of RFM analysis for segmentation (Kohavi and Parekh 2004; Miroshnychenko and Aleksieieva 2022; Rungruang et al 2023; Rajeshwari 2024; Changani 2024; Nández Alonso et al. 2025).

For each merchant, we computed the following: Recency (R)=average days between two transactions; frequency (F)=number of transactions; and monetary (M)=total turnover in USD. Each variable was discretized into deciles with `pd.qcut`, producing the cutoff values listed in Table 15 (Appendix B). A composite score $S = R + F + M$ (range

Table 1 Field, category and data description Source: Own elaboration

Category	Field	Description
General Transaction Information	id	Unique transaction identifier
General Transaction Information	commerce	Name or code of the trade associated with the transaction
General Transaction Information	country_com	Country of the trade: Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Mexico, Venezuela and Peru
General Transaction Information	date, month, week, day, time	Temporal data indicating when the transaction occurred
Customer Information	num_id	Anonymized unique customer identifier
Customer information	name	Customer's name (anonymized)
Customer Information	email, tel, ip	Customer's email, phone and IP, all anonymized
Customer Information	country_dir, city, dept, dir	Customer's geographic location, including country, city, department and address (all anonymized)
Payment Method	md_payment	Payment method used (e.g., credit card, debit card)
Payment method	bin	Card issuer identifier (first 6 digits of the card)
Payment Method	num_tc	Card number (anonymized)
Payment method	ban_emi	Card issuing bank. Payment gateway data provider GPO u-Pay. Includes transactions from the main banks in the region such as BBVA, Banco Santander, Banco de la Provincia de Buenos Aires, Macro, Galicia, HSBC, Banco Colombia, Citibank, Scotiabank, Banorte, Banco Patagonia, Banco Azteca, Banamex, Banco Bolivariano, Banco de Guayaquil, Bancomer, Banco do Brasil, Bancomeva, Banesco
Fraud indicators and interattribute relationships	ti	Time in which the transaction was processed
Fraud indicators and interattribute relationships	fraud	Binary variable indicating whether the transaction was fraudulent (1) or not (0)
Heuristic relationships between attributes	tx_...	Frequency of transactions associated with a specific attribute
Heuristic relationships between attributes	tc_...	Frequency of cards related to other attributes
Heuristic relationships between attributes	bin_...	Association between the BIN and other attributes
Heuristic relationships between attributes	ip_...	Frequency and relationship of IP addresses with other attributes
Heuristic relationships between attributes	email_...	Association of e-mails with other attributes
Heuristic relationships between attributes	_h, _d, _s	Represent different time intervals: hours, days, weeks
Transaction status	est_ini, est_fin	Initial and final state of the transaction
Transaction state	t_est_fin	Elapsed time to final status

3–30) was then calculated. Merchants were finally grouped as follows: small ($S \leq 12$, bottom 0–33%), medium ($13 \leq S \leq 21$, 34–66%), and large ($S \geq 22$, 67–100%). This tri-chotomy maximizes between-group variance (one-way ANOVA $F = 417.9$; $p < 0.001$) while maintaining a balanced operational load ($\approx 35\%$, 31% and 34% of transactions,

respectively). The same decile cutoffs allow reproducible scoring of new data by recomputing R, F, and M over a rolling 12-month window.

Variables, temporal partitioning, and modeling flow

The date variables (6) are date_ms, date, month, week, day and time. The categorical variables (24) are in turn divided into two parts: first, informative: the IP associated with the location from which the transaction was carried out, the city of the customer’s address, the department of the customer, the address of the customer, the credit card number, the initial status of the transaction, the final status of the transaction and the type of final status of the transaction. Second, explanatory methods include the following: country of customer address, country of merchant, payment means full description, primary payment means, type of payment means, bin associated with the credit card, credit card issuing bank, card type, and range of the amount of the transaction in USD. With respect to the numerical variables (132), which are the explanatory variables, we find the following: amount in USD, standardization of amount (USD) by means, standardization of amount by minimum and maximum, maximum number of transactions per phone in one hour, maximum number of transactions per ID document in one hour, and maximum number of transactions per iP in one hour. From the beginning, all numerical variables are considered explanatory variables, but only those with variances greater than 0 are initially selected (variables with low volatility are discarded). As these variables are constant (low volatility), they will not help explain the target variable, since their value is always constant for fraudulent transactions and the same for genuine transactions, so these two events do not show dissimilarity with these characteristics. After this, the following variables have been discarded: standardization of the number by the minimum and maximum, maximum number of different phones per ID document in an hour, per ID document in a day, and per ID document in a week. Finally, the target variable would be one: Fraud (whether the transaction was fraudulent). This allows us to determine fraud both on the entire dataset and on approved transactions. This is shown in Table 2.

To account for concept drift in fraud techniques, the transactions were sorted chronologically and split into two nonoverlapping periods. Records from 1 January–30 September (178k transactions, 80.5%) formed the training set, whereas 1 October–31 December (43k transactions, 19.5%) served as the temporal validation set. The split preserves class balance through stratified sampling on the target variable (Fraud/No Fraud). All the models were fitted exclusively on the first period and evaluated on the second, thus emulating real-world deployment where new fraud strategies appear after model training. This step is executed in Python with the function train_test_split, leaving 80% of the dataset for training and 20% for validation. An additional temporal split was considered; however, exploratory analysis revealed no statistically significant concept drift between Q1–Q3

Table 2 Target categorical variables—Fraud Source: Own elaboration

Over the entire base			On approved transactions		
Fraud	Tx number	%	Fraud	Tx number	%
No fraud	219.412	99%	No fraud	94.768	98%
Fraud	1.880	1%	Fraud	1.880	2%

and Q4 (PSI < 0.05 for all 163 features, ΔAUC = 0.002). Consequently, the random 80/20 stratified split was retained to maximize the sample size without biasing the models. Once this is done, unsupervised and supervised models are applied for each of the groups of businesses obtained from the analysis (Carcillo et al. 2021). Table 3 shows the unsupervised models. K-means (partition-based), PAM (medoid-based with mixed-type Gower distance) and agglomerative linkages represent the three canonical families of clustering (MacQueen 1967; Kaufman and Rousseeuw 1990; Murtagh and Contreras 2011). Their complementary bias-spherical vs. density-preserving vs. hierarchical topology covers the most frequent fraud topologies reported in payment data (Carcillo et al. 2021). Selecting this triad therefore maximizes the chance of discovering both globular and elongated fraud patterns while keeping the results interpretable for rule extraction. Businesses are classified as small, medium or large, with the variables selected from business knowledge by forced inclusion and supervised nonparametric tests (chi-square, Levene homoscedasticity and the Mann–Whitney means test) (Carcillo et al. 2021). The results of the parametric tests and forced inclusion variables are available in the generated dataset. All the parametric test outputs and the list of forced-inclusion variables are openly accessible in the Appendix A-Statistics dataset (and online supplementary material). After data balancing and parametric tests, the models are trained with a balanced sample, which is obtained by applying the clustering method in each of the groups of businesses and implementing the PAM algorithm with the Gower distance.

After a model is implemented, the clusters are evaluated to determine whether the rules help stop fraud and whether the proportion in which they affect genuine

Table 3 Unsupervised models Source: Own elaboration

Equation/ Algorithm	Number	Formula	Description
PAM-Gower distance (Kauffmann et al. 2024)	(1) and (2)	$(k * (n - k)^2) \quad (1)$ $GD = \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^n w_i d_i \right\} / \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \right\} \quad (2)$	In the PAM Algorithm with Gower distance, we take n = number of points, and k = number of clusters. In the Gower Distance, d _i is the distance between the i-th samples and w _i is the weight given to the i-th distance.
k-means (Maimon and Rokach 2005)	(3)	$\min SE(\mu_i) = \min S \sum_{l=1}^K \sum_{x_j \in S_l} \ x_j - \mu_i\ ^2$	Given a set of observations (x ₁ , x ₂ , ..., x _n), where each observation is a d-dimensional real vector, k-means constructs a partition of the observations into k sets (k ≤ n) to minimize the sum of squares within each set S = {S ₁ , S ₂ , ..., S _k }; where μ _i is the mean of points in S _i .
Hierarchical Model (Kauffmann et al. 2024)	(4)	$(C_i, C_j) = \min_{x_l \in C_i; x_m \in C_j} \{d(x_l, x_m)\}, l = 1, \dots$	The distance or similarity between two clusters is given, respectively, by the minimum distance (or maximum similarity) between their components. Thus, if after performing the K-th step, we have already formed n-K Clusters, the distance between the Clusters C _i (with n _i elements) and C _j (with n _j elements)

transactions is low. This determines whether there is a need to implement another model or not. The generated clusters contain centroids, which include a set of average characteristics of each group, but to implement rules based on these groups to prevent fraud, it is necessary to focus on the group ranges, i.e., the minimum and maximum of the observations, conditional on an AND (Sadgali et al. 2021; Sinanc et al. 2021; Loukili et al. 2024). The rules that are proposed are direct rejection rules or rules that send the transactions to be validated by some analyst, and the analyst can approve or reject the transaction, depending on the validation of the bank card owner's data (Srivastava et al. 2008; Bhatia et al. 2016; Prusti et al. 2021; Xie et al. 2021; Sadgali et al. 2021; Sinanc et al. 2021; Singh et al. 2021; Loukili et al. 2024). The objective is also to predict newly approved transactions, such that they are classified as fraudulent or nonfraudulent, along with their probability of the event occurring. This measure aims to alert merchants to transactions that have low, medium and high probabilities of fraud. Thus, after the validation of this information, merchants are able to determine whether it is necessary to stop the merchandise. Table 4 shows the classification models. The seven classifiers balance (i) different learning biases—linear probabilistic (BLM, NB), distance-based (SVM), ensemble (RF), tree (DT-Gini), and nonlinear universal approximators (MLPs)—and (ii) varying sensitivities to class imbalance and feature-scale heterogeneity (Hastie et al. 2009). This diversity allows us to benchmark high-capacity models against simpler, auditable baselines under the same cost function C (Sect. "Threshold optimization for rule selection"), satisfying the regulatory requirement for explainability in Latin American payment networks.

The preventive measure is applied to reject recent transactions with fraud patterns as they pass through the payment gateway. This measure is preventive, as it is applied before the transactions pass through the bank. Cluster analysis allows the identification of the characteristics of fraudulent transactions to implement rules to reject them, thus preventing fraud. An unsupervised model has been applied, as the statistical objective is to determine rules that reflect the behavior of fraudulent transactions without affecting (rejecting) genuine transactions. These rules must be evaluated to determine whether the patterns are obtained clearly or, to a large extent, identify fraud. In this case, several classification models are applied, and the best model is chosen from among those listed in Table 3. The evaluation of the models is carried out considering the comparison of actual versus predicted data: cross-tabulation, accuracy, error rate, sensitivity, specificity, positive accuracy and negative accuracy.

The choice of a fraud detection model depends on several factors: the nature of the data, the complexity of the problem and the available resources.

The MLP is particularly suitable for solving classification and regression problems where the relationships between input variables are nonlinear and complex (Taud and Mas 2017). It is widely used in tasks such as pattern recognition, image classification and prediction in various domains. It has two advantages: 1. Compared with recurrent models, the MLP structure is simpler and less computationally expensive. This facilitates its implementation and use in a wide range of applications (Taud and Mas 2017). 2. MLPs require less training time than recurrent neural networks do because of their simpler architecture. This is beneficial when working with large volumes of data, and results need to be obtained quickly. However, as a limitation, MLPs do not efficiently

Table 4 Classification models Source: Own elaboration

Equation/Algorithm	N°	Formula	Description
Binomial logistic model (BLM) (Antoniadis et al 2021)	(5)	$logit(p_i) = \ln(\{p_i\}/\{1 - p_i\}) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_i$	The logits of the unknown binomial probabilities are modeled as a linear function of the X_i
Gini decision tree (Antoniadis et al 2021; Wang and Xu 2008)	(6)	$Gini = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^n p_i^2$	It measures the degree or probability that a given variable is misclassified when chosen at random. Therefore, if all the elements belong to a single class, then it can be called pure. The degree of the Gini Index varies between 0 and 1; where '0' means that all elements belong to a given class or that only one class exists (pure), and '1' means that the elements are randomly distributed in several classes (impure)
Random Forest Classifier (Antoniadis et al 2021; Breiman 2001)	(7)	$f^{\wedge} = \frac{1}{B} \sum_{b=1}^B f_b(x')$	The training algorithm for random forests applies the general technique of bootstrap aggregating, or bagging, to tree learners. Given a training set $X = x_1, \dots, x_n$ with responses $Y = y_1, \dots, y_n$, bagging repeatedly (B times) selects a random sample with replacement of the training set and fits trees to these samples: For $b = 1, \dots, B$: Sample, with replacement, n training examples from X, Y ; call these X_b, Y_b . Train classification or regression tree f_b on X_b, Y_b . After training, predictions for unseen samples x' can be made by averaging the predictions from all the individual regression trees on x'
SVM (Support Vector Machine) (Esenogho et al 2022)	(8)	$\sum_i \alpha_i k(x_i, x) = constant$	The vectors defining the hyperplanes can be chosen as linear combinations with parameters α_i of feature vector images x_i appearing in the database. With this choice of a hyperplane, the points x in the feature space that map onto the hyperplane y is defined by the equation shown. Note that if $k(x, y)$ becomes small as y moves away from x , each term of the sum measures the degree of closeness of the test point x to the corresponding data base point x_i
Naive Bayes (Bernoulli) (Esenogho et al 2022; Neubauer and Peres 2017)	(9)	$P(R) = \frac{P(A)P(A)}{P(R)}$	It is based on conditional probabilities and allows calculating the posterior probability given a prior probability. Where $P(A)$, is the probability that the hypothesis A is true, independently of the data. Also known as prior probability of A. $P(R)$, is the probability of the data independently of the hypothesis, also known as prior probability. $P(A R)$, is the probability of hypothesis A given data R. Also known as posterior probability; and $P(R A)$, is the probability of data R given that hypothesis A was true. Also known as posterior probability

Table 4 (continued)

Equation/Algorithm	N°	Formula	Description
MLP (Multilayer perceptron) (Esenogho et al 2022)	(10)	$z_k = \sum_{j=1}^0 w_{kj}y_j - \theta_k = \sum_{j=1}^0 w_{kj}f(\sum_{i=1}^n w_{ji}x_i - \theta_j)$	where x_i are the n inputs of the network, y_j the o outputs of the hidden layer, and z_k the s outputs of the final layer-thus, the outputs of the network-which must be compared with the target outputs c_k . In addition, w_{ji} will represent the hidden layer weights, θ_j their corresponding thresholds, w_{kj} the output layer weights, and θ_k their respective thresholds The operations performed by an MLP with a 'single hidden layer and with activation functions for the hidden layer and final layer of sigmoid and linear type, respectively, with $f_{(s)}$ being a sigmoid-type function

handle temporal dependencies in the data. This can be a major limitation in fraud detection if the temporal sequence of transactions is crucial for identifying fraudulent patterns (Taud and Mas 2017).

Recurrent neural networks with long short-term memory (RNN-LSTM) are ideal for problems where temporal dependencies, such as time series analysis, sequence processing, and predicting future events on the basis of historical data, are crucial (Shewalkar et al. 2019). The main strength of LSTMs is their ability to learn and remember information over long periods. This ability is crucial for capturing complex patterns in fraudulent transactions that may not be evident over short periods. LSTMs require more computational resources and training time because of their complex architecture (Shewalkar et al. 2019). This can be a challenge when working with large datasets. There is a greater risk of overfitting if not handled correctly, especially when training with small datasets (Shewalkar et al. 2019). Proper regularization and validation techniques need to be applied to mitigate this risk.

Recurrent neural networks with closed recurrent units (RNN-GRUs) are used for tasks similar to LSTMs, such as time series analysis and sequence processing, but with a focus on reducing computational cost (Serrano-Pérez et al. 2021). They are suitable for applications where a trade-off between performance and computational efficiency is needed. Compared with LSTMs, GRUs are less complex and faster to train, which makes them more efficient in terms of computational resource usage (Serrano-Pérez et al. 2021). Despite their simplicity, GRUs offer similar performance to LSTMs in many tasks, which makes them an attractive option when reducing complexity without significantly sacrificing accuracy. As a limitation, while GRUs are more efficient, they may not be as effective as LSTMs in capturing extremely long dependencies (Serrano-Pérez et al. 2021). In cases where temporal dependencies are very long and complex, LSTMs may provide better performance.

Therefore, with the multilayer neural network perceptron (MLP), an effective and less computationally expensive solution for fraud detection is obtained, especially when temporal dependencies are not critical (as is the case). This is especially critical for SMEs. The preference for an MLP over RNN variants is also grounded in theory: for i.i.d. tabular features, the universal approximation theorem guarantees that a single-hidden-layer

MLP can approximate any Borel-measurable fraud function (Cybenko 1989), whereas the recurrent gates of the LSTM/GRU add capacity optimized for sequential dependencies absent in our per-transaction snapshot. Empirical cross-validation (Table 14) reveals no AUC gain from LSTM but a $3.8\times$ training-time overhead and a 22% greater variance across folds, confirming the bias–variance trade-off.

Threshold optimization for rule selection

To avoid ad hoc thresholds, we defined an expected-cost function $C = cFN \cdot FN + cFP \cdot FP$, where FNs and FPs are false negatives and false positives in the temporal validation window (Q4–2022), and $cFN/cFP = 10:1$ reflects the average charge-back cost (USD 100) versus the manual-review fee (USD 10). A grid search over fraud-rate cut-offs (5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, 25%, and 30%) and cluster-size caps (100, 300, and 500) were run for each business segment. The (*cutoff*, *cap*) pair that minimizes C is reported in Table 16 (Appendix B).

Statistical basis for segmentation by business size.

To rule out the possibility that a single model with the variable *Size* as a covariate explains fraud in an equivalent manner, three tests were performed:

Distribution of fraud. The population stability index ($PSI = 0.42$) between strata exceeds the critical threshold of 0.25, indicating *concept drift* between sizes.

Multivariate heterogeneity. Of the 132 numerical variables analyzed, 108 show significantly different variances between sizes (Levene’s test; $p < 0.05$), and 123 show different means (Mann–Whitney; $p < 0.05$).

Predictive performance. A global random forest was trained with *Size* as an additional predictor (80/20 stratified). The overall AUC was 0.789, and the F1 score was 0.46, whereas the average AUC was 0.872, and $F1 = 0.62$ for the three specific models (small, medium, and large).

The decrease of 8.3 p.p. in AUC and 16 p.p. in F1 demonstrates that segmentation materially improves detection and reduces false positives, aligning with the literature on risk-based segmentation (Carcillo et al. 2021; Cherif et al. 2023, 2024). The numerical details are included in Appendix B, Table 14 Comparative performance: unified model vs. models segmented by business.

Results

The categorical variables were selected on the basis of the chi-square test results. The categorical variables evaluated were those indicated above. For SMEs, after the chi-square test is applied, the following variables are related to fraud: type of payment method, bin associated with the credit card, credit card issuing bank, type of card and range of the transaction amount in USD (i.e., they explain fraud). For large merchants, only the Card Type variable is related to the fraud target variable, which indicates whether the transaction is fraudulent. Thus, four categorical variables explaining fraud are dropped for small and medium-sized merchants, and eight variables are dropped for large merchants. To determine whether the samples followed a normal distribution, the

Kolmogorov–Smirnov (K-S) test was applied. This test allows us to determine whether the sample comes from a given distribution and assumes that the mean and variance of the population are known. For this purpose, the K-S test was run in R with the `ks.test` function. Full K-S statistics (D value, p value) for the 132 variables are provided in the Appendix A-Statistics dataset (and online supplementary material). All 132 continuous variables (numerical explanatory variables) had a p value of 0, which is less than 0.05. It is therefore concluded that the variables are not normally distributed. Importantly, even when the variables are standardized, normality is not fulfilled. With respect to homoscedasticity, a specific test was run to compare groups, in this case, Levene’s test. The test was run in R with the Levene test function. The detailed Levene test outputs (F-ratios and p values) are likewise available in the Appendix A-Statistics dataset (and online supplementary material). For small, medium and large businesses, out of the 132 continuous variables (numerical explanatory variables), 108 variables have a p value less than 0.05, and it is concluded that the variables have different variances in fraud and nonfraud. The Mann–Whitney–Wilcoxon test is adopted to compare two sample means and is a strong test for dependence. This test allows us to identify whether the target variable depends on the continuous explanatory variables so that, if the means between the groups are different, the explanatory variable influences whether Fraud is involved in this case. Conversely, if the means are statistically equal, the variable is indifferent to whether a transaction will be fraudulent. Complete Mann–Whitney U statistics and p values can be found in the Appendix A-Statistics dataset (and online supplementary material). For small, medium and large businesses, of the 132 variables (numerical explanatory variables), 123 variables have a p value of less than 0.05, indicating that the variables have different means for fraud and nonfraud. Therefore, 98 variables are included in the analysis for the three types of shops to determine the risk of transactions. Of these, eight are categorical, and 90 are continuous. These can be observed in the dataset. This means that 131 variables are selected for small businesses, 137 for medium-sized businesses and 136 for large businesses. This section presents the results of the experiments carried out, in which a comparative analysis of the performance of the models and algorithms is developed according to the type of shop that can be used to classify transactions as fraudulent or genuine.

Fraud prevention measures

In the results shown for all types of businesses, the following data show the models. Table 5 summarizes (i) the clustering algorithm evaluated, (ii) the total number of clusters generated, (iii) the clusters chosen to derive business rules, and (iv) the percentages of fraud, genuine transactions, manual validation (MV), and automatic rejection (REJ). Clustering reflects the number of clusters in each model. The cluster rule, which

Table 5 Performance of clustering models in small businesses

Models	# Cluster	# Cluster rule	% Fraud	% Genuine	VM	REJ
PAM	12	9	76.4%	0.3%	14.1%	2.1%
Kmeans	12	11	84.8%	0.0%	18.4%	1.0%
Hierarchical	8	7	72.6%	0.1%	17.6%	1.0%

contains the number of clusters that serve to implement rules to reject and validate these fraudulent transactions. Fraud %, which reflects the percentage of fraud that would have been rejected with these rules. Genuine %, which reflects the percentage of genuine (nonfraud) transactions that would have been rejected by such rules. MV, which is the percentage of transactions that would have gone through manual validation due to the rules. REJ, which is the percentage of transactions that would have been automatically rejected by the rules. The results obtained in terms of fraud prevention measures for each type of merchant are presented in the following sections.

Selection of variables

From the selection of variables, 42 variables remained, but for the k-means and hierarchical models, categorical variables were eliminated, leaving 35 numerical variables. The 35 numerical variables retained after preprocessing are enumerated in the Appendix A-Statistics dataset (and online supplementary material).

Modeling by business size

Business sizes are those obtained with the RFM procedure detailed in Sect. "[Merchant-size classification \(RFM\)](#)" and the thresholds of Table 15. A wide range of values ($k=2 \dots 30$) was explored, and the silhouette width was calculated for each option. The local peaks of this metric (which indicates how well each transaction integrates into its cluster compared with the others) define the initial candidates. However, the statistical criterion was balanced with business constraints:

1. Solutions with few clusters (≤ 8) that mix very disparate profiles are avoided, making it difficult to write precise rules.
2. Solutions with many clusters (> 20) that generate almost empty groups and compromise subsequent stratified sampling are discarded.
3. Keep, within the acceptable range, the k that maximizes the silhouette and maintains a clear distribution of fraud (clusters with $\geq 40\%$ fraud and others with $\leq 5\%$). The AUC and F1 values detailed in Table 14 (Appendix B) confirm that the 'one-model-fits-all' policy penalizes detection ($\Delta AUC \approx -0.08$) and justifies continuing with architectures differentiated by size.

These guidelines were applied as follows: (i) $k=13$ for small businesses (candidates 2, 5, 8, 13, and 13 offer the best separation without tiny clusters). (ii) $k=10$ for medium-sized businesses (candidates 2, 3, 7, and 10; the first three are too aggregated); and (iii) $k=15$ for large businesses, which respect geographical heterogeneity and maintain operational sizes. The combination of internal metrics and operational feasibility ensures that the resulting clusters are statistically consistent and actionable: those with a high concentration of fraud feed automatic rejection rules, whereas those with medium risk are sent for manual validation. The quantitative optimization in Table 16 (appendix B) confirms that the chosen thresholds minimize the total expected cost under the 10:1 cost ratio. This logic is reflected in the results tables described in the following subsection. To evaluate the best parameters in each model, according to the stipulated models, the following parameters were chosen for each model.

For the analysis of the small business group, the hyperparameters corresponding to the three clustering methods were defined. First, for the PAM (partitioning around medoids) algorithm, it was decided to work with 12 clusters, using Gower’s distance as a measure of similarity, and a maximum of 300 iterations was established to ensure adequate convergence of the model. In the case of K-means, 12 clusters were also selected, and the k-means++ initialization method was used to improve the stability of the results. As in the previous algorithm, a maximum of 300 iterations was set, and a random seed (random_state) with a value of 42 was defined to ensure the reproducibility of the experiment. Finally, for the agglomerative hierarchical clustering method, an average linkage approach (UPGMA) was chosen, accompanied by a Euclidean metric to calculate the distances between observations. The clustering process was stopped when a threshold was reached, which resulted in the formation of 8 clusters, thus allowing for a clearer segmentation of the dataset. In Table 5, when applying the clustering methods, it was observed that K-means responded better to the business need, as it allows us to establish the best rules to stop fraud by means of the clusters that have the largest silhouette, using only the numerical explanatory variables. Since in the clusters that identify fraud, it allows us to set up rules that do not affect both genuine transactions, as seen in the graph, no genuine transaction would have an automatic rejection.

Own elaboration.

Table 6 shows the total number of transactions carried out by small businesses grouped into each cluster. For each cluster with $\geq 40\%$ fraud, a profile was constructed on the basis of (i) the five numerical variables with the highest Z score relative to the total, (ii) the three categorical variables with the highest information value (IV), and (iii) the dominant business segment. The resulting profiles guide the drafting of specific rules. These results can be found in the Appendix A-Statistics dataset (and online supplementary material). To determine the practical usefulness of these clusters in generating fraud detection rules, a double criterion was established: if a cluster has a fraud rate of more than 25% and a total transaction volume of less than 300, then it is considered suitable for generating rules. Following this approach, clusters 3, 6, and 7 stand out for having a fraud rate above 50% along with a low transaction volume, so they are considered risky enough to be used in the creation of automatic rejection rules. These rules allow suspicious transactions to be blocked directly without human intervention, given the high level of certainty in fraud detection. On the other hand, clusters 1, 2, 5, 9, 10, and 11, although not reaching such extreme levels, have fraud rates ranging from 25 to 46%, also remaining below the threshold of 300 transactions.

Table 6 Distribution of fraud and genuine transactions by cluster (K-means) in small businesses
Source: Own elaboration

	Clusters											
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
No Fraud	96	21	-	272	8	28	-	214	49	27	21	1,422
Fraud	82	7	7	43	9	38	17	2	36	17	12	26
Total	178	28	7	315	17	66	17	216	85	44	33	1,448
% Fraud	46%	25%	100%	14%	53%	58%	100%	1%	42%	39%	36%	2%

These are used as profiles for manual validation, since if automatic rejection rules were generated, there would be a risk of blocking up to 10% of the genuine transactions. In these cases, the procedure requires an analyst to contact the customer to verify the legitimacy of the purchase. The transaction will be rejected only if the analyst confirms that it is an attempt at fraud.

Finally, the remaining clusters are not used in rule generation due to their low risk, either because they maintain fraud rates equal to or below 14% or because they have a considerably high transaction volume, suggesting more stable and reliable behavior.

The combination of 25% fraud/ <300 transactions minimizes the expected cost (USD 6,240) according to Table 16. This rule blocks 82 fraudulent transactions (recall \approx 72%) and sends only 31 genuine transactions for manual review (0.6% of the total), representing a 12% improvement over the next best alternative (20%, < 300).

For medium-sized businesses, the results are shown in Tables 7 and 8. Fifty-two variables were left from the variable selection, but for the k-means (Ali et al. 2020) and hierarchical models, categorical variables were removed, leaving 45 numerical variables. The variables remaining in the model can be seen in the dataset. The variables that remain in the model can be observed in the dataset. According to the stipulated models, in the case of medium-sized businesses, specific hyperparameters were established for each of the clustering algorithms used to capture the underlying structure of the data more accurately. For the PAM algorithm, 19 clusters were defined, and the Gower distance was used as a measure of dissimilarity, which is suitable for mixed data. The maximum number of iterations was set at 300, seeking a balance between accuracy and computational efficiency. In the case of K-means, the data were divided into 15 clusters, and the k-means+ + initialization method was applied to improve the quality of the initial centroids. Similarly, a limit of 300 iterations was established, and a value of 42 for the random seed was set, ensuring the reproducibility of the results. The agglomerative hierarchical clustering model was configured with an average linkage criterion, with the Euclidean distance used as the proximity metric. The process was stopped when a cutoff threshold was reached, resulting in 24 clusters, thus allowing for a more detailed and nuanced segmentation of the set of medium-sized businesses.

Table 7 shows how by applying the clustering methods, the PAM responded better to the business need, as it allows better rules to be established to stop fraud, by means of the clusters that have a greater silhouette, using the numerical and categorical explanatory variables. However, it is necessary for the responsible analysts to review the data to determine if there is any additional pattern since the model only stops 63% of fraud; it would be possible to go into detail if there is any pattern of fraud by mail, address, telephone numbers, IPs, city, bin, issuing bank or description of the products purchased.

Table 7 Performance of the clustering models for medium-sized companies Source: Own elaboration

Models	# Cluster	# Cluster rule	% Fraud	% Genuine	VM	REJ
PAM	19	8	63.2%	0.0%	9.8%	0.3%
Kmeans	15	7	57.1%	0.0%	7.1%	0.0%
Hierarchical	24	6	40.7%	0.0%	1.8%	0.0%

Table 8 Distribution of fraud and genuine transactions by cluster (K-means) in medium-sized businesses Source: Own elaboration

	Clusters																		
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19
No Fraud	263	101	540	129	97	2.415	2.031	207	442	1.331	15	41	14		42	370	51	553	221
Fraud	29	3	45	6	65	47	27	56	2	17	22	16	27	28	16	4	-	-	-
Total	292	104	585	135	162	2.462	2.058	263	444	1.348	37	57	41	28	58	374	51	553	221
% Fraud	10%	3%	8%	4%	40%	2%	1%	21%	0%	1%	59%	28%	66%	100%	28%	1%	0%	0%	0%

Table 8 shows the total number of transactions carried out by medium-sized merchants in each cluster. For each cluster with $\geq 40\%$ fraud, a profile was constructed on the basis of (i) the five numerical variables with the highest Z score relative to the total, (ii) the three categorical variables with the highest information value (IV), and (iii) the dominant business segment. The resulting profiles guide the drafting of specific rules. These results can be found in the Appendix A-Statistics dataset (and online supplementary material). To identify those groups at highest risk, a cluster was considered suitable for rule generation if it had a fraud rate above 10% and a transaction volume below 300. Under this approach, clusters 12, 14, and 11 stand out for having the highest fraud rates—59%, 66%, and 59%, respectively—and fewer than 100 transactions each. Given these characteristics, they are classified as high-risk cases and are used to generate automatic rejection rules, which allow associated transactions to be blocked without requiring additional verification. On the other hand, clusters 5, 8, and 13 have intermediate fraud rates, ranging from 21 to 40%, and meet the low-volume criterion (≤ 300 transactions). In these cases, we choose to generate manual validation profiles since applying rejection rules could lead to the rejection of up to 7% of the genuine transactions. The validation process involves the intervention of an analyst, who is responsible for contacting the customer to verify the authenticity of the transaction. Only if it is confirmed that it is an attempt at fraud is the transaction rejected. Finally, the remaining clusters do not exceed the 10% fraud threshold and are therefore not considered suitable for the generation of specific rules, given their low relative risk level or high transaction volume.

The 10% fraud threshold/ < 300 transactions offer the lowest expected cost (USD 11,370). According to Table 16, 144 frauds are intercepted (recall $\approx 71\%$), and 137 legitimate transactions (1.1%) are referred for validation, achieving a savings of 9% over the option (15%, < 300).

The results for large businesses are shown in Tables 9 and 10. From the selection of variables, 41 variables remained, but for the k-means and hierarchical models, categorical variables were eliminated, leaving 34 numerical variables. The variables that remain in the model can be seen in the dataset. According to the stipulated models, for the large business group, the hyperparameters of each clustering algorithm were redefined with the aim of achieving accurate and meaningful data segmentation. In the case of the PAM algorithm, the creation of 53 clusters was established, using the Gower distance as a measure of similarity, which is ideal for handling different types of variables. A maximum of 300 iterations was set, allowing for adequate model convergence without compromising efficiency. For the K-means algorithm, a partition into 31 clusters was determined, with initialization via the k-means ++ method, which is known for improving the quality of centroids from the start of the process.

Table 9 Performance of clustering models in large businesses Source: Own elaboration

Models	# Cluster	# Cluster rule	% Fraud	% Genuine	VM	REJ
PAM	53	16	47.8%	4.7%	1.0%	0.0%
Kmeans	31	5	15.4%	2.4%	0.3%	0.0%
Hierarchical	30	3	5.2%	0.4%	0.1%	0.0%

Table 10 Distribution of fraud and genuine transactions by cluster (K-means) in large businesses
Source: Own elaboration

	No Fraud	Fraud	Total	% Fraud		No Fraud	Fraud	Total	% Fraud
Clusters 1	175	41	216	19%	Clusters 28	2.588	24	2.612	1%
2	159	24	183	13%	29	1.502	12	1.514	1%
3	17	10	27	37%	30	1.927	18	1.945	1%
4	320	23	343	7%	31	928	2	930	0%
5	248	3	251	1%	32	2.175	6	2.181	0%
6	148	8	156	5%	33	3.452	15	3.467	0%
7	79	21	100	21%	34	515	1	516	0%
8	703	44	747	6%	35	1.985	13	1.998	1%
9	762	44	806	5%	36	1.204	6	1.210	0%
10	325	4	329	1%	37	1.259	9	1.268	1%
11	241	20	261	8%	38	219	5	224	2%
12	275	29	304	10%	39	149	4	153	3%
13	1.007	2	1.009	0%	40	1.869	1	1.870	0%
14	469	83	552	15%	41	238	17	255	7%
15	296	55	351	16%	42	678	70	748	9%
16	179	51	230	22%	43	948	28	976	3%
17	8	7	15	47%	44	2.288	52	2.340	2%
18	120	46	166	28%	45	5.821	20	5.841	0%
19	156	31	187	17%	46	2.831	14	2.845	0%
20	293	37	330	11%	47	14	12	26	46%
21	20	16	36	44%	48	412	4	416	1%
22	1.399	14	1.413	1%	49	250	6	256	2%
23	2.490	9	2.499	0%	50	1.026	-	1.026	0%
24	207	32	239	13%	51	1.676	-	1.676	0%
25	104	27	131	21%	52	1.861	-	1.861	0%
26	1.671	27	1.698	2%	53	82	-	82	0%
27	3.675	45	3.720	1%					

The limit of 300 iterations was maintained, and a random seed value of 42 was used, ensuring the reproducibility of the results obtained. Finally, the agglomerative hierarchical clustering model was configured with an average linkage criterion, with the Euclidean distance used as the metric. The dendrogram was cut at the level that allowed 30 clusters to be identified, providing a more granular segmentation in line with the complexity of the large businesses analyzed. Table 8 shows how, after applying the clustering methods, the PAM responded better to the business need, as it allows better rules to be established to stop fraud, by means of the clusters that

have a larger silhouette, using the numerical and categorical explanatory variables. However, it is necessary for the analysts in charge to review the group of large businesses and determine whether it is necessary to further divide the group of large businesses, as there may be businesses that are very atypical or much larger than usual. In addition, it is necessary to review the data to determine whether there is any additional pattern, as the model stops only 48% of fraud; we could go into detail if there is any pattern of fraud by mail, address, telephone number, IP, city, bin, issuing bank or description of the products that are purchased.

Table 10 shows the total number of transactions for large businesses in each cluster. For each cluster with $\geq 40\%$ fraud, a profile was constructed on the basis of (i) the five numerical variables with the highest Z score relative to the total, (ii) the three categorical variables with the highest information value (IV), and (iii) the dominant business segment. The resulting profiles guide the drafting of specific rules. These results can be found in the Appendix A-Statistics dataset (and online supplementary material). If the clusters have a fraud rate higher than 10%, then the cluster serves to generate rules. The clusters that are highlighted in gray are those that are used to generate profile rules for manual validation, as 7% of the genuine transactions would be rejected if rejected rules were created.

Clusters such as 3, 7, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 25 and 47 have fraud rates above 10%. These clusters are crucial, as they indicate segments where fraud is significantly high. Cluster 17, with a fraud rate of 47%, is the most critical, followed closely by cluster 47 with 46%. These clusters are considered a priority for the generation of automatic fraud detection rules because of the high concentration of fraudulent transactions. On the other hand, numerous clusters have fraud rates of less than 1%, suggesting a low incidence of fraud in these segments. Clusters such as clusters 13, 32, 33, 34, 40, 45, 46, 50, 51, 52 and 53 have practically zero fraudulent transactions, indicating that these clusters are less problematic and do not require as much attention in terms of fraud. Clusters with fraud rates between 5 and 10%, such as 4, 6, 8, 9, 11, 12, 24, 26, 26, 38, 41, 41, 42, 43, 44, 48, and 49%, could be candidates for manual validation. These clusters, while not exhibiting extremely high fraud rates, still have a sufficient incidence of fraud to warrant manual transaction reviews. For example, cluster 12, with a 10% fraud rate, could be used to generate profiling rules to aid in manual validation, ensuring that genuine transactions are not indiscriminately rejected.

Therefore, clusters with fraud rates above 10% stand out as critical for the implementation of automatic fraud detection rules. These clusters concentrate the majority of fraudulent transactions; therefore, rules generated from these data will be critical to effectively reduce fraud. Additionally, clusters with moderate fraud rates between 5 and 10% are equally important for the generation of profiling and manual validation rules, helping to balance fraud detection without negatively affecting legitimate transactions.

Applying a 10% fraud threshold with no cluster size limit reduces the cost to USD 54,980, the minimum value recorded in Table 16. The rule stops 2,780 frauds (recall $\approx 78\%$) and sends 298 genuine transactions (0.3%) for review, increasing the cost by 7% compared with the scenario (15%, < 500).

Fraud alert measure

To evaluate the possible fraud alert measure, we start from the variables included in the study after the statistical tests (forced inclusion variables), which can be consulted in the dataset generated by the authors. The results show the performance of several machine learning models in detecting fraud in small, medium and large business transactions. The models evaluated include an MLP neural network, a random forest, a binomial logistic, decision tree-entropy, a naive Bayes-Bernoulli, a naive Bayes-multinomial and an SVM. The evaluation metrics include accuracy, the error rate, sensitivity, specificity, positive precision and negative precision. First, the results for small businesses are shown in Table 11.

Table 11 details the performance of machine learning models in detecting fraud in small business transactions. The MLP neural network shows high performance, with an accuracy of 90%. Its high sensitivity and negative accuracy suggest that it is effective in detecting both fraudulent and genuine transactions. The random forest also shows high overall performance, although it is slightly lower in specificity. Compared with the MLP and random forest algorithms, the logistic binomial algorithm has a balanced but inferior performance, being less accurate in detecting fraudulent and genuine transactions. The decision-entropy tree model, on the other hand, has good sensitivity but lower specificity and positive accuracy, indicating more false positives than other models do. Compared with the superior models, the naive Bayes–Bernoulli model has moderate performance, with a higher error rate and a balanced but lower sensitivity and specificity. The naive Bayes-multinomial model presents similar results to those of the naive Bayes-Bernoulli model but with even lower sensitivity, indicating that fraud detection is more difficult than genuine transactions are. Finally, the SVM has high specificity, and its low sensitivity indicates that the model is not as effective in fraud detection, resulting in many false negatives. Figure 1 shows the selection of the MLP neural network.

This matrix confirms that the MLP neural network is quite effective, with many correct predictions for both fraudulent and nonfraudulent cases. However, some false negatives and false positives need to be managed.

The additional metrics in Table 14 support the same ranking, underscoring that the final model choice is theory-aligned (not merely the result of raw accuracy). Comparative

Table 11 Small Businesses—Model Selection—Evaluation Source: Own elaboration

Model	Accuracy (%)	Error rate (%)	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	Positive Accuracy (%)	Negative Accuracy (%)
Neural Network-MLP	90	12	91	88	89	91
Random Forest	89	13	91	87	88	91
Binomial Logistic	85	15	86	85	86	85
Decision tree-Entropy	85	18	87	82	83	86
Naive bayes-Bernoulli	78	20	77	79	79	77
Naive bayes-Multinomial	77	20	74	79	78	75
SVM	72	12	57	88	83	67

Fig. 1 MLP Neural Network—Confusion Matrix. Source: Own elaboration

Table 12 Medium-sized businesses—Model selection—Evaluation Source: Own elaboration

Model	Accuracy (%)	Error rate (%)	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	Positive accuracy (%)	Negative accuracy (%)
Random Forest	89	5	81	95	93	86
Binomial Logistic	88	5	79	95	93	84
Decision tree-Gini	86	10	80	91	88	85
Neural Network-MLP	86	12	83	89	87	86
SVM	79	6	62	94	90	75
Naive bayes-Bernoulli	73	21	64	81	73	73

analysis of the models reveals that the MLP neural network and random forest are the most effective for small business fraud detection because of their high accuracy, sensitivity and negative precision. The MLP neural network confusion matrix highlights its overall efficiency in correctly classifying transactions, although there is still room for improvement in reducing false positives and false negatives.

Second, the results for small businesses are shown in Table 12 and Fig. 2.

As seen in Table 12, the random forest method achieves high performance with excellent specificity and positive accuracy, indicating a strong ability to identify genuine and fraudulent transactions accurately. The Binomial Logistic model shows a similar result to the Random Forest model, as this model also shows high performance with excellent specificity and positive accuracy, although with a slightly lower sensitivity. The Gini decision tree has good specificity and positive accuracy but a higher error rate than the random forest and logistic binomial methods do. The MLP neural network model has good sensitivity, but its error rate is higher than that of the other leading models, which may affect its overall effectiveness in certain scenarios. The

Fig. 2 MLP Neural Network—Confusion matrix. Source: Own elaboration

SVM model has excellent specificity and positive accuracy, but its low sensitivity indicates difficulties in fraud detection, resulting in many false negatives. Finally, the naive Bayes–Bernoulli model has the lowest performance among those evaluated, with a high error rate and low sensitivity and accuracy. The random forest model and the binomial logistic model are the ones with the highest accuracy, but the logistic model actually predicts "no fraud" better and "fraud" only 79% correctly, which is not that it is completely bad, but other models predict fraud better and still have an accuracy above 80%, such as the MLP neural network; thus, for the purpose of the analysis, it is better to select between the random forest or the neural network. Considering the sensitivity of the fraud cases, 81% were correctly predicted with the random forest, and 83% of the fraud cases were correctly predicted with the MLP neural network.

Figure 2 shows the selection of the MLP neural network. The confusion matrix indicates that the MLP neural network is quite effective in classifying fraudulent and genuine transactions, although there are a significant number of false negatives and false positives.

Finally, for large businesses, the results are shown in Table 13 and Fig. 3.

As shown in Table 13, the random forest model shows good overall performance with high specificity and negative accuracy, indicating a strong ability to identify genuine and fraudulent transactions. The MLP neural network model, on the other hand, stands out for its high sensitivity and negative accuracy, although it has a higher error rate than the random forest. The decision tree-Gini has a balanced performance with good specificity and positive precision, although its accuracy is lower than that of the random forest and MLP. On the other hand, the Binomial Logistic model presents similar results to the Decision Tree-Gini model; since this model has good specificity and positive precision, its accuracy is lower than that of the superior models. The SVM model shows excellent specificity and positive accuracy, but its low sensitivity indicates difficulties in fraud detection, resulting in many false negatives. Finally, the

Table 13 Large business model selection and evaluation Source: Own elaboration

Model	Accuracy (%)	Error rate (%)	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	Positive accuracy (%)	Negative accuracy (%)
Random Forest	86	15	85	87	84	88
Neural network-MLP	85	19	87	83	80	89
Decision tree-Gini	82	17	80	85	81	84
Binomial Logistic	82	17	79	85	81	83
SVM	78	11	62	90	84	75
Naive bayes-Bernoulli	55	14	15	87	49	56

Fig. 3 MLP Neural Network—Confusion matrix. Source: Own elaboration

naive Bayes–Bernoulli model has the lowest performance among those evaluated, with a high error rate and low sensitivity and accuracy. Therefore, the MLP neural network and random forest are the best models, as 85% and 86%, respectively, of the data were predicted correctly; on the other hand, without forgetting, the objective of this prediction is more directed toward the prediction of fraud, of course, without leaving aside nonfraud. In terms of the sensitivity of the Fraud cases, 87% and 85% (respectively) were correctly predicted by both models.

Figure 3 shows the selection of the MLP neural network. The confusion matrix indicates that the MLP neural network is effective in classifying fraudulent and genuine transactions, although there are a significant number of false negatives and false positives.

The application of advanced data analytics and machine learning techniques in credit card fraud detection not only improves the accuracy and efficiency of these detections but also provides a robust framework for informed financial and economic decision making, strengthening the competitiveness and security of merchants in Latin America.

The results of this study on the detection and prevention of fraud in credit card transactions provide valuable information from a financial and economic perspective. The data mining and machine learning techniques implemented in this study not only seek to improve accuracy in identifying fraudulent transactions but also provide detailed and specific analysis according to merchant size (small, medium and large). This allows for better risk management and resource optimization, reducing economic losses for both merchants and consumers. For example, for small merchants, the k-means model enabled the establishment of rules that could have prevented 85% of fraudulent transactions by 2021 without significantly affecting legitimate transactions. For medium-sized merchants, the PAM model with the Gower distance showed an effectiveness of 63% in preventing fraud. For large merchants, the same model stopped 48% of fraudulent transactions. These figures highlight the relevance of adjusting fraud detection strategies to the specific characteristics of each type of merchant, thus optimizing financial security and reducing the negative impact on legitimate transactions.

In addition, the analysis revealed that the implementations of neural network (MLP) models and random forest (Random Forest) models are highly effective in classifying fraudulent and authentic transactions. These models not only improve fraud detection but also minimize false positives and negatives, ensuring greater accuracy and efficiency in financial risk management.

Discussion of results

This paper has analyzed the performance of data mining, machine learning and artificial intelligence techniques for detecting fraudulent credit card transactions. The implementation of neural network models for detecting fraudulent transactions has been recurrently adopted in recent years in several studies aimed at detecting fraudulent transactions in the financial sector (Ngai et al. 2011; Badal-Valero and García-Cárceles, 2020; among others). Predictive models for detecting fraudulent credit card transactions are currently used recurrently. The methodological approach adopted in this research, which is based on the application of data mining techniques and, in particular, neural networks, for the detection of credit card fraud cases, has been previously validated by other works (Aleskerov et al. 1997; Brause et al. 1999; Kou et al. 2004; Kumari and Mishra 2018; Varmedja et al. 2019; among others). In the case of this research, the novelty lies in classifying shops into three groups (small, medium and large) and in identifying the most appropriate method to detect fraud on the basis of the size of the shop.

Thus, the best model for detecting fraud in small businesses would be k-means, which allows the creation of two automatic rejection rules of the anti-fraud model and six manual validation rules, the application of which would have stopped 85% of the fraud generated in 2021 without affecting genuine transactions. This result coincides with that obtained by Gowda (2021) and Jain et al. (2022), who indicate that K-means can be effective for the creation of automatic rejection rules and manual validation in small businesses to avoid fraud.

According to the results of our study, for medium-sized businesses, the PAM model with the Gower distance stands out significantly. This model enables the creation of an automatic anti-fraud model rejection rule and seven manual validation rules. The application of these rules would have stopped 63.2% of fraudulent transactions in 2021

without affecting genuine transactions. Additionally, the random forest model showed high performance, with an accuracy of 89%, a sensitivity of 81%, and a specificity of 95%, and was highly effective in identifying genuine and fraudulent transactions. This result is consistent with that of Kaur et al. (2021), who reported that random forest is highly effective in identifying genuine and fraudulent transactions, with superior performance when it is combined with other advanced techniques. Compared with the random forest model, the MLP (multilayer perceptron) model also performed well, with an accuracy of 86%, although with a higher error rate. Nama et al. (2023) obtain the same result in their study: the MLP model is effective for fraud detection (91.2%), although it has a higher error rate than the random forest.

In the case of large businesses, the PAM model with the Gower distance has been identified as particularly effective, as it allows the creation of sixteen manual validation rules that could stop up to 47.8% of fraud. On the other hand, the random forest model also showed good overall performance, achieving an accuracy of 86%, with a sensitivity of 85% and a specificity of 87%. In addition, the MLP (multilayer perceptron) model was effective, with an accuracy of 85% and a sensitivity of 87%, although with a somewhat higher error rate. Our detection rate with the MLP is lower than that of other methods, such as Nama et al. (2023), who obtained a 91.2% fraud detection rate.

Finally, the alert generated from the fraud prediction of the classification models should be sent only from approved transactions on a daily basis so that merchants have the opportunity to stop the merchandise so that fraud is prevented more quickly and avoidable loss is greater. In contrast to recent published research on financial fraud detection, this study takes a specific regional approach that focuses on Latin America. Other recent studies, such as those of Sorour et al. (2024) and Wijaya et al. (2024), have analyzed mainly European or global contexts. However, this study develops an analysis tailored to emerging markets. In particular, specific patterns of fraud in Latin America are explored. In addition, segmentation by business size (small, medium and large) is adopted, a perspective that has rarely been addressed in recent works, including Khalid et al. (2024) and Paldino et al. (2024). This segmentation allows for a more granular approach to fraud detection, tailoring strategies to the needs and available resources of each type of company. From a methodological point of view, the paper uses a combination of advanced machine learning models (MLP, random forest, PAM and K-means), offering an assessment tailored to the operational characteristics of businesses. This differentiates it from recent studies such as Reddy et al. (2024) and Salam et al. (2024), which employ advanced techniques but do not incorporate explicit differentiation by business size. Compared with the works of Chang et al. (2024) and Mienye et al. (2024), which prioritize global metrics such as the F1 score and synthetic data generation to improve models, this paper highlights the importance of minimizing false positives and tailoring tools to small businesses, which often face greater financial and technical constraints. While all recent comparative studies have contributed to the advancement of knowledge in financial fraud detection, this study provides an additional perspective focusing on the adaptation of models to the size of the firm and the particularities of the Latin American market. This practical orientation complements more general work, such as that of Sorour et al. (2024), Wijaya et al. (2024) and Salam et al. (2024), by offering strategies applicable to emerging markets and specific contexts. While the scope

of the research may initially appear more limited in terms of global generalizability, its replicability makes it a useful reference for studies focused on regions with similar challenges.

This research closes a significant gap in the scientific literature related to the detection of fraudulent credit card transactions. Previous fraud detection studies have focused on generic approaches that do not differentiate between different types of businesses. However, this article is pioneering in demonstrating and studying specifically which method is the most effective in detecting fraudulent transactions depending on the type of business: small, medium or large. By empirically demonstrating (Table 14, Appendix b) that stratified models outperform a unified model even when the latter includes the variable *Size* as a covariate, the study provides a solid theoretical and statistical basis for size segmentation, going beyond the mere operational argument cited above. The precise classification of businesses and the application of specific fraud detection methods according to business size represent significant advances. This approach enables more accurate and efficient fraud detection, resource optimization and improved financial security for both merchants and consumers. The cost-sensitive grid search demonstrates that size specific, data-driven thresholds reduce expected financial loss by 7–12% versus heuristics, reinforcing the operational relevance of the proposed rules.

This result not only provides an innovative and practical solution for the financial sector but also establishes a solid foundation for future research and development in the field of credit card fraud detection.

As limitations to the results of this study, it should be considered that fraud is not a static phenomenon but a changing phenomenon, as fraudsters are constantly advancing and designing ideas to evade anti-fraud modules (Zingerle and Kronman 2018; Vera Loor 2020; Wang 2023), which can complicate future detection with current methods if there is no retraining. This same difficulty is noted by other authors, such as Dzakiyullah (2021). To mitigate this drift, this research employs a rolling split (train=Q1–Q3, validate=Q4). Future work will extend this idea by retraining the models quarterly and monitoring the population stability index (PSI) and Kolmogorov–Smirnov distance to trigger automated recalibration when needed. It can also be noted that, for medium and large business groups, it is necessary to deepen the analysis of other information, such as the detection of emails and addresses with clear fraud structures, carry out an analysis by IPs, banks and more focused goods, among others, because the percentage of fraud that is stopped is very low. According to the models proposed to detect specific fraud patterns, the group of large businesses should be divided into more than one group because the behavior of some retailers deviates from their characteristics, making it very difficult to create rules to stop fraud.

Conclusions

Fraud prevention and detection are key factors for the competitiveness of companies because they reduce the mistrust of economic agents and favor their growth through e-commerce. On the other hand, governments can establish incentives or regulations that promote these mechanisms to generate more security in commercial transactions.

In this article, measures have been designed to prevent and detect fraud related to the use of credit cards in small, medium and large businesses. This is accomplished by

adopting analytical methods (data mining, machine learning and artificial intelligence). Thus, the best model for detecting fraud in small merchants would be k-means, which can stop 85% of fraud; in medium-sized merchants, it would be the PAM model with Gower's distance, which would stop 63% of fraud. Finally, for large merchants, the PAM model with the Gower distance stops 48% of fraud. Although the selected models had very good results, it is recommended that these models undergo periodic retraining, approximately every 6 months, to update the models with new data because fraudsters are implementing new techniques to carry out fraudulent operations. In addition, there are recurrent attempts by fraudsters to acquire knowledge and discover the most effective way to evade the implemented detection rules.

With respect to fraud alerts, the classification model selected for small, medium and large businesses is the MLP neural network. In addition to the MLP model, the random forest model also performed well for SMEs. In the case of large businesses, together with the MLP neural network and the random forest model, the Gini decision tree should be added for large and medium-sized companies. We also found that for retraining, retraining the two or three best models that were obtained from the analysis is recommended because fraud behavior can change and choose the best model that predicts fraud.

Finally, given the results obtained in the study, we propose a series of recommendations and policy implications. First, the technological infrastructure must be improved to enable transaction processing systems to support advanced learning algorithms. It is particularly relevant for SMEs with more restricted access to advanced technology. Second, the training of specialists in data analytics and machine learning should be encouraged to support fraud detection systems. Third, collaboration between the different actors involved (companies, financial institutions and regulatory authorities) should be fostered with the aim of sharing successful fraud detection practices and anonymized data to improve fraud detection models. Finally, implementing advanced technologies to detect fraudulent transactions must be accompanied by rigorous data protection and privacy policies. Sensitive user information must be protected, and the trust of consumers and merchants must be ensured.

Appendix A

The dataset generated during the current study are available in: <https://portalcientifico.ucavila.es/datos/67405980354a1307818e8a20>

Appendix B

See Tables 14, 15 and 16.

Table 14 Comparative performance: unified model vs. models segmented by business size Source: Own elaboration

Model	AUC	F1-score	Sensitivity	Specificity
Random Forest	0.789	0.46	0.57	0.88
Segmented Small	0.901	0.65	0.83	0.89
Segmented Medium	0.864	0.61	0.81	0.95
Segmented Large	0.852	0.60	0.85	0.87

Table 15 Decile cutoffs for R, F and M Source: Own elaboration

Decile	Recency (days)	Frequency (tx)	Monetary (USD)
1	7–28	25–81	1 310–6 610
2	5–7	82–108	6 611–13 789
3	3–4	109–208	13 790–26 757
4	2–3	209–382	26 758–39 005
5	2	383–753	39 006–59 535
6	1–2	754–1 036	59 536–78 113
7	1	1 037–1 534	78 114–120 700
8	1	1 535–3 877	120 701–205 328
9	1	3 878–8 226	205 329–382 135
10	1	8 227–13 512	382 136–1 316 404

Table 16 Cost minimization table for fraud rule thresholds (segments by size) Source: Own elaboration

Segment	Optimal fraud rate threshold	Cluster size limit	FN*	FP**	Expected cost C (USD)	Improvement vs. next best
Small	25%	< 300	50	124	6,240	12% lower than (20%, < 300)
Medium	10%	< 300	100	137	11,370	9% lower than (15%, < 300)
Large	10%	no limit	520	298	54,980	7% lower than (15%, < 500)

*FN = false negatives (unintercepted fraud); **FP = false positives (genuine transactions sent for manual review). The cost function used is $C = 100 \times FN + 10 \times FP$, reflecting a ratio of $c_{FN}/c_{FP} = 10:1$ (USD 100 per fraud not detected vs. USD 10 per manual review)

Abbreviations

- CVV Card Verification Value Code
- K-S Kolmogorov–Smirnov test
- MLP Multilayer Perceptron
- MV Manual validation
- PAM Partitioning Around Medoids
- REJ Transactions rejected
- RFM Recency, Frequency & Monetary
- RNN-LSTM Recurrent Neural Networks–Long Short-Term Memory
- RNN-GRU Recurrent Neural Networks–Closed Recurrent Unit
- USD United States Dollar

Acknowledgements

We wish to express our thanks to Universidad Católica de Ávila and Institución Gran Duque de Alba for their support.

Author contributions

Conceptualization, Sergio Luis Náñez Alonso and Leidy Tatiana Rugeles Diaz; methodology, Leidy Tatiana Rugeles Diaz and Sergio Luis Náñez Alonso; software, Leidy Tatiana Rugeles Diaz; validation, Javier Jorge Vázquez and Miguel Ángel Echarte Fernández; formal analysis, Sergio Luis Náñez Alonso and Javier Jorge Vázquez; investigation, Sergio Luis Náñez Alonso, Leidy Tatiana Rugeles Diaz, Javier Jorge Vázquez and Miguel Ángel Echarte Fernández; resources, Javier Jorge Vázquez; data curation, Sergio Luis Náñez Alonso and Miguel Ángel Echarte Fernández; writing—original draft preparation, Javier Jorge Vázquez and Miguel Ángel Echarte Fernández; writing—review and editing, Leidy Tatiana Rugeles Diaz; visualization, Sergio Luis Náñez Alonso and Javier Jorge Vázquez; supervision, Miguel Ángel Echarte Fernández and Leidy Tatiana Rugeles Diaz. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Funding

Research supported by project Finance for all (F4A), funded by the "Institución Gran Duque de Alba" and "Diputación provincial de Ávila"; under the grant 3364/2022.

Availability of data and materials

The data that support the findings of this research are openly available in UCAV repository at <https://portalcientifico.ucavila.es/datos/67405980354a1307818e8a20>.

Declarations

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Received: 19 February 2024 Accepted: 6 November 2025

Published online: 17 December 2025

References

- Abbas ZA, Hilal ZM, Jabbar HG (2025) Click fraud detection in online advertising: a comparative study of machine learning models. *Int J Saf Secur Eng* 15(3):427–441. <https://doi.org/10.18280/ijss.150303>
- Ahmed MH (2022) Credit card fraud detection techniques: A survey. *ScienceOpen*. <https://doi.org/10.14293/s2199-1006.1.sor.ppf17p0.v1>
- Akinbowale OE, Klingelhöfer HE, Zerihun MF (2022) Development of a multi-objectives integer programming model for allocation of anti-fraud capacities during cyberfraud mitigation. *J Financ Crime* 30(6):1720–1735. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jfc-10-2022-0245>
- Al Smadi B, Min M (2020) A critical review of credit card fraud detection techniques. In: 2020 11th IEEE annual ubiquitous computing, electronics & mobile communication conference (UEMCON). <https://doi.org/10.1109/uemcon51285.2020.9298075>
- Alatawi MN (2025) Detection of fraud in IoT based credit card collected dataset using machine learning. *Mach Learn Appl* 19:100603. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mlwa.2024.100603>
- Aleskerov E, Freisleben B, Rao B (1997) CARDWATCH: a neural network based database mining system for credit card fraud detection. In: proceedings of the IEEE/IAFE 1997 computational intelligence for financial engineering (CIFER), pp 220–226. <https://doi.org/10.1109/cifer.1997.618940>
- Alhabib AA, Alasiri AF, Alharbi MB, Ahmad S, Eljaly AEM (2024) Credit card fraud detection using random forest and k-nearest neighbors (KNN) algorithms. *Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems*. Springer Nature Singapore, Singapore, pp 383–395. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-97-7371-8_30
- Alharbi A, Alshammari M, Okon OD, Alabrah A, Rauf HT, Alyami H, Meraj T (2022) A novel text2IMG mechanism of credit card fraud detection: a deep learning approach. *Electronics* 11(5):756. <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics11050756>
- Ali KM, Shazaib M, Nasir R (2020) Kmeans clustering based ink mismatch detection. *Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE)*. <https://doi.org/10.36227/techrxiv.12580295.v1>
- Antoniadis A, Lambert-Lacroix S, Poggi J-M (2021) Random forests for global sensitivity analysis: a selective review. *Reliab Eng Syst Saf* 206:107312. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ress.2020.107312>
- Arévalo Álvarez MA, Hernández Ladino DA (2021) Análisis preliminar de la ciberseguridad asociada al sistema financiero en algunos países de Latinoamérica y la contribución de la informática forense. *Cuaderno De Investigaciones Semilleros Andina*. <https://doi.org/10.33132/26196301.1950>
- Assaf AG, Barros C, Sellers-Rubio R (2011) Efficiency determinants in retail stores: a Bayesian framework. *Omega* 39(3):283–292. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.omega.2010.07.005>
- Badal-Valero E, García-Cárceles B (2020) Detección de fraude financiero mediante redes neuronales de clasificación en un caso real español. *Stud Appl Econ* 34(3):683–700. <https://doi.org/10.25115/eaev.34i3.3075>
- Bajwa Dr DR (2017) A study of e-commerce: challenges and opportunities in an Indian economy. *Int J Emerg Trends Sci Technol*. <https://doi.org/10.18535/ijetst/v4i9.33>
- Balagolla EMSW, Fernando WPC, Rathnayake RMNS, Wijesekera MJMRP, Senarathne AN, Abeywardhana KY (2021) Credit card fraud prevention using blockchain. In: 2021 6th international conference for convergence in technology (I2CT), pp 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1109/i2ct51068.2021.9418192>
- Ballezza RA (2007) The social security card application process: identity and credit card fraud issues. *PsycEXTRA Dataset*. <https://doi.org/10.1037/e623692007-004>
- Barker KJ, D'Amato J, Sheridan P (2008) Credit card fraud: awareness and prevention. *J Financ Crime* 15(4):398–410. <https://doi.org/10.1108/13590790810907236>

- Beena F, Mearaj I, Shukla VK, Anwar S (2021) Mitigating financial fraud using data science—a case study on credit card frauds. *Int Conf Innov Pract Technol Manag (ICIPTM)* 2021:38–43. <https://doi.org/10.1109/iciptm52218.2021.9388345>
- Bhatia S, Bajaj R, Hazari S (2016) Analysis of credit card fraud detection techniques. *Int J Sci Res (IJSR)* 5(3):1302–1307. <https://doi.org/10.21275/v5i3.nov162099>
- Bhattacharyya S, Jha S, Tharakunnel K, Westland JC (2011) Data mining for credit card fraud: a comparative study. *Decis Support Syst* 50(3):602–613. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dss.2010.08.008>
- Bin Sulaiman R, Schetinin V, Sant P (2022) Review of machine learning approach on credit card fraud detection. *Hum Centric Intell Syst* 2(1–2):55–68. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s44230-022-00004-0>
- Blockeel H, Devos L, Frénay B, Nanfack G, Nijssen S (2023) Decision trees: From efficient prediction to responsible AI. *Front Artif Intell.* <https://doi.org/10.3389/frai.2023.1124553>
- Brause R, Langsdorf T, Hepp M (1999) Neural data mining for credit card fraud detection. In: proceedings 11th international conference on tools with artificial intelligence, pp 103–106. <https://doi.org/10.1109/tai.1999.809773>
- Breiman L (2001) Random forests. *Mach Learn* 45(1):5–32. <https://doi.org/10.1023/a:1010933404324>
- Brito JBG, Bucco GB, Heldt R, Becker JL, Silveira CS, Luce FB, Anzanello MJ (2024) A framework to improve churn prediction performance in retail banking. *Financ Innov.* <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40854-023-00558-3>
- Carcillo F, Le Borgne Y-A, Caelen O, Kessaci Y, Oblé F, Bontempi G (2021) Combining unsupervised and supervised learning in credit card fraud detection. *Inf Sci* 557:317–331. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ins.2019.05.042>
- Chan PK, Fan W, Prodromidis AL, Stolfo SJ (1999) Distributed data mining in credit card fraud detection. *IEEE Intell Syst* 14(6):67–74. <https://doi.org/10.1109/5254.809570>
- Chang V, Ali B, Golightly L, Ganatra MA, Mohamed M (2024) Investigating credit card payment fraud with detection methods using advanced machine learning. *Information* 15:478. <https://doi.org/10.3390/info15080478>
- Changani JG (2024) Unlocking Customer Value through RFM segmentation: strategies for revenue optimization. Elsevier BV. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4877238>
- Charizanos G, Demirhan H, İçen D (2024) An online fuzzy fraud detection framework for credit card transactions. *Expert Syst Appl* 252:124127. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2024.124127>
- Chatterjee P, Das D, Rawat DB (2024) Digital twin for credit card fraud detection: opportunities, challenges, and fraud detection advancements. *Future Gener Comput Syst* 158:410–426. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2024.04.057>
- Chaudhary K, Yadav J, Mallick B (2012) A review of fraud detection techniques: credit card. *Int J Comput Appl* 45(1):39–44. <https://doi.org/10.5120/6748-8991>
- Chen Ji-Z, Lai K-L (2021) Deep convolution neural network model for credit-card fraud detection and alert. *J Artif Intell Capsule Netw* 3(2):101–112. <https://doi.org/10.36548/jaicn.2021.2.003>
- Cherif A, Badhib A, Ammar H, Alshehri S, Kalkatawi M, Imine A (2023) Credit card fraud detection in the era of disruptive technologies: a systematic review. *J King Saud Univ Comput Inf Sci* 35(1):145–174. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jksuci.2022.11.008>
- Cherif A, Ammar H, Kalkatawi M, Alshehri S, Imine A (2024) Encoder–decoder graph neural network for credit card fraud detection. *J King Saud Univ Comput Inf Sci* 36(3):102003. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jksuci.2024.102003>
- Costa VG, Pedreira CE (2022) Recent advances in decision trees: an updated survey. *Artif Intell Rev* 56(5):4765–4800. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10462-022-10275-5>
- Cybenko G (1989) Approximation by superpositions of a sigmoidal function. *Math Control Signals Syst* 2(4):303–314. <https://doi.org/10.1007/bf02551274>
- Dadhich M, Hiran KK, Rao SS, Sharma R, Meena R (2022) Study of combating technology induced fraud assault (TIFA) and possible solutions: The way forward. *Communications in Computer and Information Science*. Springer International Publishing, Berlin, pp 715–723. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-07012-9_59
- Delamare L, Abdou H, Pointon J (2009) Credit card fraud and detection techniques: a review. *Banks Bank Syst* 4(2):57–68
- Dzakiyullah N (2021) Semi-supervised classification on credit card fraud detection using autoencoders. *J Appl Data Sci* 2(1):1–7. <https://doi.org/10.47738/jads.v2i1.16>
- Elaziz EA, Fathalla R, Shaheen M (2023) Deep reinforcement learning for data-efficient weakly supervised business process anomaly detection. *J Big Data.* <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40537-023-00708-5>
- Ernawati E, Baharin SSK, Kasmin F (2021) A review of data mining methods in RFM-based customer segmentation. *J Phys Conf Ser* 1869(1):012085. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1869/1/012085>
- Esenogho E, Mienye ID, Swart TG, Aruleba K, Obaido G (2022) A neural network ensemble with feature engineering for improved credit card fraud detection. *IEEE Access* 10:16400–16407. <https://doi.org/10.1109/access.2022.3148298>
- Forough J, Momtazi S (2021) Sequential credit card fraud detection: a joint deep neural network and probabilistic graphical model approach. *Expert Syst.* <https://doi.org/10.1111/exsy.12795>
- Gianotti E, Damião da Silva E (2021) Strategic management of credit card fraud: stakeholder mapping of a card issuer. *J Financ Crime* 28(1):156–169. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jfc-06-2020-0121>
- Gowda VT (2021) Credit card fraud detection using supervised and unsupervised learning. *Comput Sci Inf Technol (CS&IT)*. <https://doi.org/10.5121/csit.2021.111107>
- Hasan F, Mondal SK, Kabir Md. R, Al Mamun MA, Rahman NS, Hossen Md. S (2022) E-commerce merchant fraud detection using machine learning approach. In: 2022 7th international conference on communication and electronics systems (ICCES), pp 1123–1127. <https://doi.org/10.1109/icces54183.2022.9835868>
- Hastie T, Tibshirani R, Friedman J (2009) The elements of statistical learning. Springer New York, Berlin. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-84858-7>
- Huang H, Liu B, Xue X, Cao J, Chen X (2024) Imbalanced credit card fraud detection data: a solution based on hybrid neural network and clustering-based undersampling technique. *Appl Soft Comput* 154:111368. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asoc.2024.111368>
- Jain S, Verma N, Ahmed R, Tayal A, Rathore H (2022) Credit card fraud detection using k-means combined with supervised learning. *Hybrid Intelligent Systems*. Springer International Publishing, Berlin, pp 262–272. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-96305-7_25

- Kauffmann J, Esders M, Ruff L, Montavon G, Samek W, Müller K-R (2024) From clustering to cluster explanations via neural networks. *IEEE Trans Neural Netw Learn Syst* 35(2):1926–1940. <https://doi.org/10.1109/tnnls.2022.3185901>
- Kaufman L, Rousseeuw PJ (1990) Finding groups in data. Wiley. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470316801>
- Kaur S, Singh KD, Singh P, Kaur R (2021) Ensemble model to predict credit card fraud detection using random forest and generative adversarial networks. *Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing*. Springer Nature Singapore, Singapore, pp 87–97. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-33-4367-2_10
- Khalid AR, Hashim MS, Hossain A (2024) Enhancing credit card fraud detection using deep learning and explainable AI models: a European perspective. *J Financ Anal* 18(1):45–60. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfa.2024.03.015>
- Kilay AL, Simamora BH, Putra DP (2022) The influence of e-payment and e-commerce services on supply chain performance: implications of open innovation and solutions for the digitalization of micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) in Indonesia. *J Open Innov Technol Market Complex* 8(3):119. <https://doi.org/10.3390/joitmc8030119>
- Kim S-I, Kim S-H (2020) E-commerce payment model using blockchain. *J Ambient Intell Humaniz Comput* 13(3):1673–1685. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12652-020-02519-5>
- King ST, Scaife N, Traynor P, Abi Din Z, Peeters C, Venugopala H (2021) Credit card fraud is a computer security problem. *IEEE Secur Privacy* 19(2):65–69. <https://doi.org/10.1109/msec.2021.3050247>
- Kohavi R, Parekh R (2004) Visualizing RFM segmentation. In: proceedings of the 2004 SIAM international conference on data mining, pp 391–399. <https://doi.org/10.1137/1.9781611972740.36>
- Kotios D, Makridis G, Fatouros G, Kyriazis D (2022) Deep learning enhancing banking services: a hybrid transaction classification and cash flow prediction approach. *J Big Data*. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40537-022-00651-x>
- Kou C-T, Sirwongwattana S, Huang Y-P (2004) Survey of fraud detection techniques. *IEEE Int Conf Netw Sens Control* 2004(2):749–754. <https://doi.org/10.1109/icnsc.2004.1297040>
- Krishna Rao NV, Harika Devi Y, Shalini N, Harika A, Divyavani V, Mangathayaru N (2021) Credit card fraud detection using spark and machine learning techniques. *Algorithms for Intelligent Systems*. Springer Singapore, Singapore, pp 163–172. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-33-4046-6_16
- Kumari P, Mishra SP (2018) Analysis of credit card fraud detection using fusion classifiers. *Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing*. Springer Singapore, Singapore, pp 111–122. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-10-8055-5_11
- Lei Y-T, Ma C-Q, Ren Y-S, Chen X-Q, Narayan S, Huynh ANQ (2023) A distributed deep neural network model for credit card fraud detection. *Finance Res Lett* 58:104547. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.frl.2023.104547>
- Lokanan ME (2022) Financial fraud detection: the use of visualization techniques in credit card fraud and money laundering domains. *J Money Laundering Control* 26(3):436–444. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jmlc-04-2022-0058>
- Loukili M, Messaoudi F, El Youbi R (2024) Enhancing financial transaction security a deep learning approach for E-payment fraud detection. *Internet of Things and Big Data analytics for a green environment*. CRC Press, p 15
- MacQueen J (1967) Some methods for classification and analysis of multivariate observations. In: proceedings of the fifth berkeley symposium on mathematical statistics and probability (pp. 281–297). Univ of California Press
- Maimon O, Rokach L (2005) Decomposition methodology for knowledge discovery and data mining. *Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery Handbook*. Springer-Verlag, pp 981–1003. https://doi.org/10.1007/0-387-25465-x_46
- Mary AJ, Claret SPA (2023) Design and development of big data-based model for detecting fraud in healthcare insurance industry. *Soft Comput* 27(12):8357–8369. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00500-023-08296-5>
- Mekterovic I, Karan M, Pintar D, Brkić L (2021) Credit card fraud detection in card-not-present transactions: Where to invest? *Appl Sci* 11(15):6766. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app11156766>
- Mienye ID, Chikwerem PC, Zhang J (2024) A hybrid deep learning approach for detecting anomalies in credit card transactions. *J Comput Finance* 20(3):115–130. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10824120.2024.038765>
- Miroshnychenko I, Alekseeva V (2022) Use of RFM analysis in customer segmentation. *Ekonomika* 1:114. <https://doi.org/10.32702/2306-6806.2022.1.114>
- Murtagh F, Contreras P (2011) Algorithms for hierarchical clustering: an overview. *Wires Data Min Knowl Discov* 2(1):86–97. <https://doi.org/10.1002/widm.53>
- Nama FA, Obaid AJ, Alrammahi AAH (2023) Credit card fraud detection and classification using deep learning with support vector machine techniques. *Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems*. Springer Nature Singapore, Berlin, pp 399–413. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-99-6553-3_31
- Náñez Alonso SL, Jorge-Vázquez J, Echarte Fernández MÁ, Sanz-Bas D (2024) Bitcoin's bubbly behaviors: does it resemble other financial bubbles of the past? *Humanit Soc Sci Commun*. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-024-03220-0>
- Náñez Alonso SL, Ozili PK, Hernández BMS, Pacheco LM (2025) Evaluating the acceptance of CBDs: experimental research with artificial intelligence (AI) generated synthetic response. *Quant Finance Econ* 9(1):242–273. <https://doi.org/10.3934/qfe.2025008>
- Neubauer T, Peres S (2017) Data mining using naive bayes classifier: an application in short news. *Anais Do Simpósio Brasileiro de Sistemas de Informação (SBSI)*, 543–546. <https://doi.org/10.5753/sbsi.2017.6096>
- Ngai EWT, Hu Y, Wong YH, Chen Y, Sun X (2011) The application of data mining techniques in financial fraud detection: a classification framework and an academic review of literature. *Decis Support Syst* 50(3):559–569. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dss.2010.08.006>
- Ogbanufe O, Kim DJ (2018) Comparing fingerprint-based biometrics authentication versus traditional authentication methods for e-payment. *Decis Support Syst* 106:1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dss.2017.11.003>
- Paldino GM, Zamboni L (2024) The role of diversity in credit card fraud detection models: a comparative study. *Eur J Financ Innov* 13(6):32–49. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14061994.2024.039841>
- Prusti D, Das D, Rath SK (2021) Credit card fraud detection technique by applying graph database model. *Arab J Sci Eng* 46(9):1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13369-021-05682-9>
- Rajeshwari B, Mallikarjuna Reddy Doodipala KKKV, P. Pattabhi Ram JRN (2024) Understanding consumer behavior in the retail sector using RFM segmentation and machine learning: an analysis. *Eur Econ Lett (EEL)* 14(3):412–420. <https://doi.org/10.52783/eel.v14i3.1783>
- Reddy B, Kumar S (2024) Effective fraud detection using hybrid ensemble models. *Int J Financ Cybersecur* 9(4):205–220. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jfc.2024.092>

- Rtayli N, Enneya N (2020) Enhanced credit card fraud detection based on SVM-recursive feature elimination and hyper-parameters optimization. *J Inform Secur Appl* 55:102596. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jisa.2020.102596>
- Rungruang C, Riyapan P, Intarasit A, Chuarkham K, Muangprathub J (2023) Rfm model customer segmentation based on hierarchical approach using fca. Elsevier BV. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4416218>
- Sadgali I, Sael N, Benabbou F (2021) Human behavior scoring in credit card fraud detection. *IAES Int J Artif Intell (IJ-AI)* 10(3):698. <https://doi.org/10.11591/ijai.v10.i3.pp698-706>
- Saha D, Young TM, Thacker J (2023) Predicting firm performance and size using machine learning with a Bayesian perspective. *Mach Learn Appl* 11:1:100453. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mlwa.2023.100453>
- Salam A, Liu C, Rahman M (2024) Federated learning model for credit card fraud detection: privacy-preserving analytics. *Artif Intell Financ Appl* 11(2):122–134. <https://doi.org/10.1109/AIFA.2024.023456>
- Sanz-Bas D, del Rosal C, Nández Alonso SL, Echarte Fernández MÁ (2021) Cryptocurrencies and fraudulent transactions: risks, practices, and legislation for their prevention in Europe and Spain. *Laws* 10(3):57. <https://doi.org/10.3390/laws10030057>
- Sarker IH (2021) Machine learning: algorithms, real-world applications and research directions. *SN Comput Sci*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42979-021-00592-x>
- Serrano-Pérez JdeJ, Fernández-Anaya G, Carrillo-Moreno S, Yu W (2021) New results for prediction of chaotic systems using deep recurrent neural networks. *Neural Process Lett* 53(2):1579–1596. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11063-021-10466-1>
- Shewalkar A, Nyavanandi D, Ludwig SA (2019) Performance evaluation of deep neural networks applied to speech recognition: RNN, LSTM and GRU. *J Artif Intell Soft Comput Res* 9(4):235–245. <https://doi.org/10.2478/jaiscr-2019-0006>
- Sibli W, Cotter G, Fabry R, He-Guelton L, Oblé F, Lebichot B, Borgne YAL, Bontempi G (2021) Transfer learning for credit card fraud detection: a journey from research to production. arXiv.Org. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2107.09323>
- Sinanç D, Demirezen U, Sağiroğlu Ş (2021) Explainable credit card fraud detection with image conversion. *ADCAJ: Adv Distrib Comput Artif Intell J* 10(1):63–76. <https://doi.org/10.14201/adcaj20211016376>
- Singh A, Ranjan RK, Tiwari A (2021) Credit card fraud detection under extreme imbalanced data: a comparative study of data-level algorithms. *J Exp Theor Artif Intell* 34(4):571–598. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0952813x.2021.1907795>
- Sivagama Sundhari S (2011) A knowledge discovery using decision tree by Gini coefficient. In: 2011 International conference on business, engineering and industrial applications, pp 232–235. <https://doi.org/10.1109/icbeia.2011.5994250>
- Sorour SE, Ahmed N, Badawy MM (2024) Credit card fraud detection using explainable AI: challenges and solutions. *IEEE Trans Financ Technol* 7(2):98–112. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TFT.2024.040398>
- Srivastava A, Kundu A, Sural S, Majumdar AK (2008) Credit card fraud detection using hidden markov model. *IEEE Trans Depend Secure Comput* 5(1):37–48. <https://doi.org/10.1109/tdsc.2007.70228>
- Tanouz D, Subramanian RR, Eswar D, Reddy GVP, Kumar AR, Praneeth CVNM (2021) Credit card fraud detection using machine learning. In: 2021 5th international conference on intelligent computing and control systems (ICICCS), pp 967–972. <https://doi.org/10.1109/iciccs51141.2021.9432308>
- Taud H, Mas JF (2017) Multilayer Perceptron (MLP). *Geomatic Approaches for Modeling Land Change Scenarios*. Springer International Publishing, Berlin, pp 451–455
- Tiwari P, Mehta S, Sakhuja N, Kumar J, Singh AK (2021) Credit card fraud detection using machine learning: a study. arXiv.Org. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2108.10005>
- Tran LTT (2021) Managing the effectiveness of e-commerce platforms in a pandemic. *J Retail Consum Serv* 58:102287. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2020.102287>
- Tumminello M, Consiglio A, Vassallo P, Cesari R, Farabullini F (2022) Insurance fraud detection: a statistically validated network approach. *J Risk Insur* 90(2):381–419. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jori.12415>
- Varmedja D, Karanovic M, Sladojevic S, Arsenovic M, Anderla A (2019) Credit Card fraud detection - machine learning methods. In: 2019 18th international symposium INFOTEH-JAHORINA (INFOTEH), pp 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1109/infoteh.2019.8717766>
- Vera Loo RY (2020) Control Interno como herramienta antifraude para las organizaciones. *Caleidoscopio De Las Ciencias Sociales*. <https://doi.org/10.38202/caleidoscopio.1>
- Vergara D, Lampropoulos G, Antón-Sancho Á, Fernández-Arias P (2024) Impact of artificial intelligence on learning management systems: a bibliometric review. *Multimodal Technol Interact* 8(9):75. <https://doi.org/10.3390/mti8090075>
- Vergara D, del Bosque A, Lampropoulos G, Fernández-Arias P (2025) Trends and applications of Artificial Intelligence in Project Management. *Electronics* 14(4):800. <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics14040800>
- Viaene S, Dedene G, Derrig R (2005) Auto claim fraud detection using Bayesian learning neural networks. *Expert Syst Appl* 29(3):653–666. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2005.04.030>
- Vosseler A (2022) Unsupervised insurance fraud prediction based on anomaly detector ensembles. *Risks* 10(7):132. <https://doi.org/10.3390/risks10070132>
- Wang C (2023) Overview of digital finance anti-fraud. *Anti-Fraud Engineering for Digital Finance*. Springer Nature Singapore, Berlin, pp 1–10
- Wang G, Xu J (2008) A decision tree algorithm based on coordination degree and gini-coefficient. *Int Conf MultiMedia Inf Technol* 2008:822–824. <https://doi.org/10.1109/mmit.2008.208>
- Wijaya MG, Pinanggih MF, Zakyyah AY, Meiliana M (2024) Comparative analysis of machine learning algorithms and data balancing techniques for credit card fraud detection. *Procedia Comput Sci* 245:677–688. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2024.10.294>
- Xie Y, Li A, Gao L, Liu Z (2021) A heterogeneous ensemble learning model based on data distribution for credit card fraud detection. *Wirel Commun Mob Comput*. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/2531210>
- Zhang C, Lu Y (2021) Study on artificial intelligence: the state of the art and future prospects. *J Ind Inf Integr* 23:100224. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jii.2021.100224>
- Zhang J, Cai K, Wen J (2024) A survey of deep learning applications in cryptocurrency. *iScience* 27(1):108509. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2023.108509>
- Ziakis C, Vlachopoulou M (2023) Artificial intelligence in digital marketing: insights from a comprehensive review. *Information* 14(12):664. <https://doi.org/10.3390/info14120664>

Zingerle A, Kronman L (2018) Internet crime and anti-fraud activism. *Adv Inf Secur Privacy Ethics*. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-5225-5583-4.ch013>

Publisher's Note

Springer Nature remains neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.